

1
2 **Lessons Learned on Participatory Syndromic Surveillance in Bat Guano Farming**
3 **Communities in Kang Meas District, Kampong Cham Province, Cambodia**
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6 **Abstract**

7 **Background**

8 This study investigates the possible transmission of coronaviruses between man and animals in
9 bat farming communities, a growing industry in Cambodia. Bat guano farming using artificial
10 and natural roosts involves only one species of insectivorous bat, the lesser Asiatic yellow bat
11 (*Scotophilus kuhlii*). Bat guano farming presents unknown levels of zoonotic disease risks.
12 Biological testing in this species to date has not detected any beta coronaviruses or other
13 zoonotic pathogens of major concern. Participatory syndromic surveillance (PSS) offers a
14 community-based approach that can complement the sensitivity and timeliness of traditional
15 disease surveillance and offers a One Health approach to coordinated surveillance in man and
16 animals. This paper shares the lessons learned from implementing PSS in Cambodian bat guano
17 farming communities that targeted a respiratory syndromic case definition. The findings are
18 valuable for local and international public health actors and researchers seeking to address
19 similar challenges.

20 **Methods**

21 The USAID STOP Spillover program implemented PSS in Cambodian bat guano farming
22 communities, emphasizing community involvement, trust-building, and a One Health approach.
23 Participatory epidemiology tools were used to collect qualitative data and identify cases based on

24 community-defined case definition for respiratory disease that would be expected to include
25 coronavirus infection, if present. Ninety eight humans, and 363 of livestock, bat guano, and urine
26 samples were collected for coronavirus detection. The study was started from December 2023
27 until July 2024.

28 **Results**

29 PSS effectively fostered trust between communities and One Health stakeholders through open
30 communication leading to increased case detection. The study identified alpha coronavirus and
31 COVID cases in humans, alpha coronavirus in bats, and bovine coronavirus in cattle. Notably,
32 the highest prevalence of positive coronavirus cases was found in adults and females, with rates
33 of 10.20% and 11.22% respectively. Additionally, bovine coronavirus was detected in cows,
34 indicating the potential for cross-species transmission to other ruminants and humans. However,
35 only alpha coronavirus was identified in bat guano samples. The results were shared with
36 communities and relevant government stakeholders.

37 **Conclusion**

38 PSS, combined with the One Health approach, is a valuable tool for early warning of zoonotic
39 disease threats in bat guano farming communities. The study highlights the importance of
40 community engagement, trust-building, and ongoing surveillance to mitigate risks and prevent
41 future outbreaks. The findings also emphasize the need for continued monitoring of coronavirus
42 prevalence. Although no cross-species transmission was detected, the potential for cross species
43 transmission of alpha and bovine coronaviruses exists.

44 Trial registration

45 Not applicable

46 Keywords

47 Participatory Syndromic Surveillance, One Health approach, Participatory Epidemiology tools,

48 Coronaviruses surveillance

49 **Background**

50 The shift toward alternative sources of chemical fertilizers has significantly increased the value
51 and popularity of bat guano in Cambodia’s agricultural sector. Renowned for its rich nutrient
52 content, bat guano commands a high price, making its production and sale a viable source of
53 livelihood for communities [1] . In Kampong Cham province, particularly in Kang Meas, artificial
54 bat roosts have been constructed to facilitate bat guano farming. This initiative spans three villages
55 including Varint 1, Varint 2, and Varint 3 encompassing 17 bat guano farms. These villages
56 comprising farms support 654 households, with a total population of 2,368, according to the 2023
57 commune statistics [2]. Household interviews conducted as part of a study on zoonotic spillover
58 risks in bat guano farms and communities revealed that domestic animals, including cattle, pigs,
59 chickens, dogs, cats, and bats, frequently entered homes in both bat guano producing areas
60 (BGPHs) and non-bat guano producing areas (NBGPHs). Specifically, 87.5% of BGPH
61 households and 76.4% of NBGPH households reported such intrusion [3]. In the realm of public
62 health, traditional disease surveillance methods, which rely on confirmed cases identified through
63 laboratory testing, often face limitations due to reporting delays and limited geographic coverage.
64 In addition to potential bat-associated coronaviruses, some food and surface samples tested
65 positive for Infectious Bronchitis Virus (IBV), a common gamma coronavirus of poultry [4]. The
66 effectiveness of PSS based on participatory development approaches hinges on several key factors.

67 Community participation is essential to generate first-hand information that enhances the
68 representativeness of surveillance and accurately reflects events on the ground. Local knowledge
69 and perceptions provide early detection and important insights into events [5]. By enabling earlier
70 detection of outbreaks and informing public health interventions, PSS empowers communities to
71 become active participants in safeguarding public health [6]. To prevent outbreaks, community
72 participation is essential for generating firsthand information that enhances the representativeness
73 of surveillance and accurately reflects real-world events, particularly in bat guano farming
74 communities like Kang Meas, Kampong Cham province, where zoonotic disease risks are
75 prevalent. This participatory approach is crucial for effective public health management. This
76 paper aims to share lessons learned for international public health and policy-making actors on
77 how to conduct and utilize participatory syndromic surveillance in bat guano farming
78 communities, both in Cambodia and other countries. Additionally, it assists international
79 researchers in identifying the hazards and level of risk associated with bat guano farming
80 communities in Cambodia.

81 **Methods**

82 The program was conducted from December 2023 - July 2024 in 4 different quarters. The first
83 quarter was focused on capacity building of the surveillance team at the interface level along with
84 the field activities. There were three rounds of data collections and coronavirus surveillance from
85 human, livestock and bat farms which were conducted in January, March and June respectively in
86 relation to different bat seasons. This program was piloted in Kang Meas district Kampong Cham
87 province, Cambodia targeted bat guano farming communities in three villages including Varint1,
88 Varint2, and Varint3. The whole process of the study was described in Fig.1.

89

90 **Fig. 1 Process flow of PSS for coronavirus detection in bat guano farming communities**

92 **Participatory Epidemiology Tools**

93 To collect the qualitative data leading to the detection of cases Participatory Epidemiology (PE)
94 tools including semi-structured interview (SSI), proportional piling, seasonal calendar, mapping
95 and transect walk [7] were used for collecting data and used for case findings following the case
96 definition of Febrile Respiratory Illness (FRI). The case definition used was set up from the
97 community assessment which was mandatory with fever exceeding 38 °C with at least two
98 symptoms including mucus, sore throat, muscle pain, cough, and short breathing [8].

99 **Trust building**

100 In this study, with the respective manner, the objective of the program was clearly introduced to
101 the communities. The expression of sharing ownership of the program with communities was
102 evidenced to make the community trusted and feel comfortable in the surveillance activities. The
103 communities were recruited as the key actors to report their disease syndrome for capturing the

104 firsthand information in their communities to reflect the event on the ground. Localization
105 approaches by collaboratively working with community leaders, community health care workers,
106 and private clinics were also incorporated to enhance the coordination work and high coverage of
107 the diseases self-reporting in the communities. The community health care worker plays a critical
108 role as a liaison of communities and project team for coronavirus case findings and samples
109 collection for laboratory test confirmation. As evidence of project sharing ownership, the
110 laboratory test results of individual communities were shared, combining with awareness raising
111 by commune health care to help the community understand about zoonotic diseases, bat-borne
112 diseases and avoid feeling of being exploited.

113 **One Health Approach**

114 One Health surveillance team from Cambodian Government Agencies, including Cambodia
115 Communicable Diseases Control department, General Directorate of Animal Health and
116 Production, National Animal Health and Production Research Institute, Ministry of Environment,
117 Provincial Health Department, Provincial Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries,
118 Health Operational District, Referral Hospital of Kang Meas district, and Roka Ar and Khchao
119 Health centers, was established. The team was trained in PSS, biosafety and sampling and actively
120 involved in the PSS in bat human interface where the surveillance activities were limited. The
121 work contributes to the Global Health Security Agenda. Human, livestock and environmental
122 samples were collected and analyzed. The results were reported to the government of Cambodia
123 (GOC) in the One Health sector to get advice for further case investigation and response.

124 **Sample collection and laboratory test confirmation**

125 In this study, the purposive sampling method for SSI was used based on targeted sample
126 collection criteria. Eighty-eight of Human samples and 363 of livestock, bat guano and urine
127 samples were collected for coronavirus detection. The two consensus PCR targeted RdRp gene
128 [9] were used followed by Sanger sequencing for strain characterization (Macrogen, Inc., Seoul,
129 Republic of Korea).

130 **Statistical Analysis**

131 The detected cases were analyzed by age and gender. Symptoms of reported cases were analyzed
132 using Microsoft Excel while the association analysis of the disease transmission in bat-human-
133 livestock was performed through Phylogenetic tree analysis using MEGA 11.

134 **Results**

135 **Case reporting, demography and laboratory test confirmation**

136 A total of 180 participants with 85 females and 20 girls were interviewed in PSS. Fifty Five
137 percent of participants participated in the study . Ninety percent of cases were reported to
138 community health care providers and community leaders. The participants of the study program
139 were individuals older than one-year old and under 80 years old who had experienced symptoms
140 consistent with the case definition in Fig.2.

141

142 **Fig.2**

143

(a) The age distribution of participants in PSS with (b) experience of symptoms consistent with case definition.

Table. 1 Cases reported in three different bat seasonal stages and communities' activities exposure with bat and livestock in relation to positivity of CoV detected by PCR tests

144

		% of cases identified in PSS in different bat seasonal season			(%) Positive CoV by PCR test (n=98)
		Juvenile (January) (n=22)	Pregnancy (March) (n=31)	Lactation (June) (n=45)	
Inclusion criteria (%)	Met FRI's case definition	50.00	48.39	42.22	6.12
	Family member in close contact with suspected cases	50.00	51.61	57.78	10.20
	Asymptomatic cases	31.82	35.48	15.56	1.02
Gender (%)	Female	59.09	48.39	57.78	11.22
	Male	40.91	51.61	42.22	7.14
Age (years old)	Child (0-12)	18.18	25.81	20.00	4.08
	Adolescence (13-18)	18.18	9.68	13.33	1.02
	Adult (19-59)	18.18	41.93	53.34	10.20
	Elders (60 and over)	45.46	22.58	13.33	3.06
	Cleaning livestock/cage (%)	10.20	8.16	9.18	1.02
	Feeding livestock (%)	10.20	8.16	15.31	4.08
	Experience bats enter house/kitchen (%)	19.39	14.29	16.33	7.14
	Collecting bat guano (%)	8.16	2.04	5.10	0
	Eating sick or dead livestock (%)	0	0	0	0
	Eating bat (%)	0	0	0	0

145 The reported cases and laboratory show a significant importance of CoV surveillance in bat
 146 guano communities and public health. The findings of suspected cases provided useful
 147 information about the disease's trend which indicated the level of risk in the bat guano farming
 148 communities in complement to the passive surveillance at public health institutions. The self-
 149 reporting syndrome by communities guided the team to identify the association between human,
 150 livestock and bat guano farms for risk reduction intervention and preventing outbreak. The
 151 comparison trend of number of cases, human, livestock and bat guano farm identified in PSS and
 152 confirmed laboratory cases were illustrated in Fig.3.

153 **Fig.3 The number of human cases, family member in close contact, livestock and bat guano**
 154 **farm identified in PSS and confirmed laboratory cases in different bat season**

155
 156
 157

158 **Community engagement**

159 The USAID STOP Spillover PSS program demonstrated the effectiveness of One Health
160 surveillance using participatory methods. The approach established an environment of mutual trust
161 and respect between the community and One Health stakeholders that led to greater case detection
162 and an openness for bidirectional communication and mutual behavior change. The perceptions of
163 mistrust and feelings of anxiety on the part of the community, external researchers and government
164 officials were reduced leading to a better alignment of expectations and interactions. The
165 community developed a better appreciation for biosafety and approaches to safeguarding their
166 health through good hygiene while the professionals involved developed a clearer understanding
167 of the value and a more accurate understanding of the risks involved in bat guano farming. The
168 participatory outreach to find cases in the community directly contributed to these improved
169 interactions and resulted in a much larger and more representative sample of cases for evaluation.
170 These are positive lessons that show how the development and institutionalization of integrated
171 One Health surveillance activities that incorporate participatory methods can lead to more
172 appropriate, sensitive and representative surveillance outcomes.

173 In addition, the level of trust was significantly increased while the commune health care provider
174 shared individually the laboratory test results within them either positive or negative results. The
175 communities expressed their appreciation of the project to share project ownership with the
176 community which is the core value and goal of the program as evidence. The duration of
177 availability for result sharing to communities was between 37 to 38 days and the result on
178 satisfaction from communities with the additional feedback and recommendation from the
179 survey was described in Table 2.

180 **Table. 2**

Bat seasonal stage	Sample collection duration	Reached laboratory duration	Available lab results	GOC reporting and approval duration	Result share to community	% Satisfaction	% Dissatisfaction
Bat juvenile season	5 days	1 day	24 days	1 day	7 days	80.00	20 ^a
Bat pregnancy season	4 days	1 day	13 days	1 day	18 days	90.00	10 ^b
Bat lactation season	4 days	1 day	28 days	1 day	3 days	99.00 ^d	3 ^c

Comments from dissatisfied participants due to the result seem to be a little bit late, but communities feel impressed because they knew about the result of their health and would like the project team also to share the test result of livestock and bat guano tests.

b Comments from dissatisfied participants due to livestock and bat guano were not informed at the same time.

c Comments from dissatisfied participants due to livestock and bat guano were not available to share with them.

d Awareness program on zoonotic diseases and prevention measures should come right after the program ends.

181 **Discussion**

182 **Implications of the findings**

183 Overall, the findings from PSS and confirmed laboratory test of coronavirus surveillance
 184 conducted in the bat guano farming in Kang Meas underscore the effectiveness of using
 185 participatory and One Health approaches. The results from trust building with communities and
 186 community leaders unveil the barriers and misperception that leads to greater community

187 engagement, more sensitive and representative surveillance on the ground. As a result of
188 participatory learning in the course of implementation, the surveillance and project personnel
189 gained new insights into guano farming and transcended their preconceptions concerning the
190 guano farming activity. The cases identified with symptoms and asymptomatic cases from
191 human, livestock and bat guano farms were well aligned with positive CoV by PCR test [10].
192 This indicated the significance of participatory approach complemented to the public and OH
193 health surveillance system [11,12]. This granularity provides valuable insights into the diverse
194 ways in which community engagement and OH institutionalization may be incorporated together
195 for an effective zoonotic disease outcome because only through community participation in the
196 surveillance system will viable results be achieved.

197 Importantly, our exploration of the interplay between risk and susceptibility of different age and
198 sex of bat guano farming communities to CoV unveils a significant finding of high or low risk, a
199 high number of cases is linked to the adult age group [13] and female population [14,15]. This
200 age and gender add depth to our understanding, suggesting that the target in people in working
201 age intervention may be especially impactful in these demographic subgroups [16,17,18].

202 The findings were consistent with the PREDICT 2 studies, where only alpha coronaviruses were
203 detected in farmed bat feces. Other coronaviruses such as SAR COV2, and BCoV were
204 identified as alphacoronavirus in humans, livestock and non-farmed bat species[19,20,21]. The
205 virus strains did not indicate cross transmission among human bats. However, BCoV has rarely
206 been known to have the ability for cross species transmission to other ruminants and humans that
207 cause severe diarrhea [22] and the risk of virus mutation always exists. Risk reduction
208 interventions appropriate to all livestock farming should be employed to avoid spillover risk.

209 However, the different strains of CoV in human, cow and bat feces from *Scotophilus kuhlii* in
210 these communities does not mean that bat roosts of other bat species are safe. The samples from
211 other bat species collected in Battambang, Kampong Cham, Mondulkiri, Preah Vihear, Pursat,
212 Ratanakiri, and Stung Treng were tested. Two bat were detected positive for viruses closely
213 related to SARS-CoV-2, and were morphologically identified as *Rhinolophus shameli* [23] . This
214 virus strain of this species was known to cause major risk to humans. Continued and expanded
215 surveillance of bats and other key wild animals in Cambodia is thus a crucial component of
216 future pandemic preparedness and prevention [24].

217 **Limitations of the study**

218 The study findings did not estimate the prevalence of diseases due to the small sample size. The
219 small samples can be more susceptible to bias, leading to inaccurate estimates of disease
220 prevalence or incidence. The delay of laboratory tests resulted in animal and bat limited capacity
221 of the surveillance team for further disease investigation and reporting into the integrated One
222 Health surveillance system. This limitation may affect the quality of information and data
223 sharing across One health sectors and joint response process. Since the duration of the study is
224 short, the correlation study of disease prevalence with breeding season was not conducted so the
225 findings from this study cannot evidence the association of bat-borne diseases during breeding
226 season.

227 **Conclusions**

228 Participatory learning approaches, participatory case detection, community engagement and OH
229 institutionalization were highly effective in breaking down perceptions of mistrust against
230 external researchers and government officials. Risk is dependent on the presence of hazards and

231 exposure. Although there is exposure to bats on bat guano farms, repeated studies have not
232 documented the presence of major hazards in the bats farmed in artificial and tree roosts in South
233 East Asia. The failure to identify hazards any more severe than those found in other species of
234 livestock suggests that the level of risk posed on guano farm collection is similar to that of other
235 forms of animal agriculture. The thread of coronavirus mutation is always present. Through a
236 participatory approach to the zoonotic surveillance, guano producers themselves are the first
237 actor to inform the health authority of possible future spillover. In addition, self-protective
238 measures such as hygiene practice and using Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) should be
239 employed as in all animal agriculture. These build a foundation to deal with future outbreak
240 rapidly, effectively at local level.

241 **List of Abbreviations**

242 **BCoV:** Bovine Coronavirus

243 **CoV:** Coronavirus

244 **IBV:** Infectious Bronchitis Virus

245 **IACUC:** Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee

246 **PPE:** Personal Protective Equipment

247 **PSS:** Participatory Syndromic Surveillance

248 **OH:** One Health

249 **GOC:** Government of Cambodia

250 **RdRp:** RNA-dependent RNA polymerase

251 **SARS-CoV-2:** Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus

252 **Declarations**

253 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

254 This study was approved by the National Ethics Committee of Health Research (NECHR).

255 The informed consent to participate in the study was obtained from participants (or their parent
256 or legal guardian in the case of children under 16. For animal study, the study was approved by
257 GDAHP of the Ministry of Agriculture Forestry and Fisheries in Cambodia. The livestock
258 sampling in 2024 was authorized by the Provincial Department of Agriculture, Forestry, and
259 Fisheries (PDAFF) of Kampong Cham and IACUC protocol for STOP Spillover. The informed
260 consent from the client or owner and adherence to a high standard (best practice) of veterinary
261 care were obtained.

262 **Consent for publication**

263 Not Applicable.

264 **Availability of data and materials**

265 The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon
266 reasonable request. All relevant data, including raw data, processed data, and supplementary
267 materials, have been stored securely and can be accessed by researchers who meet the criteria for
268 access to confidential data.

269 The datasets generated and analyzed during the current study are not publicly available due to
270 privacy and ethical restrictions but are available from the corresponding author on reasonable

271 request. This ensures that the data is used responsibly and ethically, in line with the consent
272 provided by the participants.

273 For further inquiries or to request access to the data, please contact the corresponding author at
274 malen.ken@tetrattech.com. We are committed to transparency and openness in our research and
275 will provide the necessary data to support replication and further investigation of our findings.

276 **Competing interests**

277 The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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303 **Contributions**

304 M.K, J.C.M and C.S contributed substantially to the conceptualization and design of the study.
305 M.K performed and had primary responsibility for all data management, statistical analysis,
306 interpretation of the findings, and writing and revising the manuscript. T.B, B.MS.C and B.C
307 assisted with the statistical analysis, interpretation of findings, and drafting and revising the
308 manuscript critically for important intellectual content. J.C.M contributed substantially with
309 interpretation of findings and writing and revising the manuscript. J.P, F.N,B.C, R.C and T.H
310 assisted with writing and revising the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final
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